

World Biodiversity Forum 2024 – Resolution

Davos, Switzerland June 20, 2024

Adopted by acclamation by the participants of the third World Biodiversity Forum.

The World Biodiversity Forum 2024, held from 16 to 20 June 2024 in Davos, Switzerland, (<https://worldbiodiversityforum2024.org/>) gathered more than 800 leading researchers, practitioners, entrepreneurs, artists, and policymakers. It was organised by bioDISCOVERY (<https://biodiscovery.earth/>), a Global Research Network (GRN) of FutureEarth (<https://futureearth.org/>), and the University of Zurich (<https://www.uzh.ch/>) and its Research Priority Programme on “Global Change and Biodiversity” (<https://www.gcb.uzh.ch/>).

The aim of the World Biodiversity Forum is to advance biodiversity research in an integrative, interdisciplinary, and transparent fashion, and to further transdisciplinary approaches in biodiversity. The forum supports and aims to accelerate transformative approaches, ranging from fundamental research to implementation, by facilitating interactions between all stakeholders relevant to biodiversity, and by integrating multiple knowledge systems.

The World Biodiversity Forum is developing into a global centre servicing the advancement of biodiversity competencies, and it is essential that it continues to be effectively and interactively supported by key stakeholders, governments, philanthropies, industries and international organisations.

The leadership and participants of the World Biodiversity Forum 2024 are concerned that

The ongoing and accelerating loss of nature and its biological diversity threatens the habitability of our planet. The interlinked biodiversity and climate crises have already impacted the tree of life, threatening more than a million species, and the health of ecosystems worldwide. We know unequivocally that excessive and unequal economic growth contributes significantly to these declines, with cascading impacts on human health and wellbeing, and volatility of the global economy. The urgent challenge now is to translate our extensive knowledge into actions that will reduce the drivers of decline, protect and restore nature, and secure the benefits to all that can flow from these actions.

The pace of action needed to meet the biodiversity and sustainability targets set for 2030 needs to accelerate if humanity is to succeed in reversing ongoing detrimental trends. Urgent and transformative action is needed to halt and reverse biodiversity loss, and redress the inequitable social and economic impacts experienced by peoples around the world. Progress will be made by recognising the reciprocity of the benefits this action entails for nature and people, building and sharing capacity and mobilising resources.

and make the following recommendations:

1. We now have at hand a large and robust body of knowledge, including indigenous knowledge, gathered by global and regional assessments on the impacts of high and excessive consumption on nature as well as the lasting benefits that flow from the protection and restoration of nature. There is an urgent need to accelerate the mainstreaming of this knowledge to inform the decisions and actions required to reach the targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KM-GBF) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The Nature Restoration Law just agreed by the European Union Environment Council aligns with the United Nations Decade of Restoration, and offers an unprecedented opportunity for international cooperation. Immediate action guided by the full breadth and diversity of knowledge systems, including traditional and scientific knowledge, will allow biodiversity and ecosystems to recover and contribute to climate action in the coming decades for the benefit of present and future generations.

2. Indigenous Peoples and local communities are at the forefront of suffering the impacts of climate change and biodiversity loss. At the same time, they need to be recognised as “stewards” of biodiversity, as, in many regions of the world, they have a strong relationship with nature and hold a deep knowledge of biodiversity and ecosystems.

3. Collaboration between science, arts, and all facets of society, incorporating multiple types of knowledge (including indigenous), creates space for a deeper inspection of the reciprocity of human-nature relationships and the exploration of existing paradigms. These collaborations open avenues for the integration of a diversity of values, and the opportunity to explore positive narratives and visions that counteract the current predominant paradigms. They create opportunities to co-develop evidence-based solutions, novel technologies and transformative pathways toward nature-positive futures for a broad range of sectors to support the implementation of biodiversity conservation and restoration.

4. Strong international collaborations that are mindful of pluralistic approaches and local contexts are key to filling gaps in knowledge and generating scientific evidence that supports action on the ground. Collaboratively and transparently generated evidence is needed to operationalize and implement global targets for biodiversity conservation, and to translate these into local action and impact. There is a clear need for alignment and policy coherence across biodiversity and climate, and the development of a common framing of these problems and sustained dialogue to advance agendas across all scales and levels of governance.

5. Current consumption and production processes of the modern world are often at the expense of biodiversity, and their transformation is needed to curtail their local and telecoupled impacts. Sustainable finance, the principle of circular and shared

economy, and general practices of responsible consumption and production that can include transformational technologies must be implemented to halt biodiversity loss and reduce impacts on climate.

6. The success of actions targeting the coupled biodiversity and climate crisis requires directly addressing the underlying societal drivers of environmental change, biodiversity loss and destruction of nature. Transdisciplinary approaches are needed that i) advance the fundamental understanding of biodiversity and habitat change, ii) attribute its changes to the underlying drivers, iii) enable societal processes to build positive narratives, contribute solutions (such as the removal of harmful subsidies) that jointly mitigate climate and biodiversity impacts, and redirect society towards sustainable futures.

The leadership and participants of the World Biodiversity Forum support the conference statement of the 7th European Congress of Conservation Biology (ECCB), held in Bologna, Italy, 17 – 21 June 2024.